

THE TYPES OF SALT AND THEIR ROLE IN BODY

Safarova Rukhsora Uygun qizi

11th grade student of Specialized
school named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

Abstract: This article is a brief overview of several different types of salt. The five types of salt this article focuses on are: Iodized Salt (Table Salt), Celtic Salt (Grey Salt), Himalayan Pink Salt, Hawaiian Red Sea Salt, Hawaiian Black Lava Salt and Crystallized rock salt. For each salt, its origin, characteristics, and common uses are discussed.

Key words: Iodized Salt (Table Salt), Celtic Salt (Grey Salt), Himalayan Pink Salt, Hawaiian Red Sea Salt, Hawaiian Black Lava Salt, Crystallized rock salt.

Introduction. Salt has an important role in our body, transporting water around and sending messages from the brain to the rest of the body. However, too much salt can lead to health issues such as raised blood pressure and higher risk of a heart attack, kidney disease and stroke.

Many foods don't seem salty but can contain hidden salt. We may add salt to our food during cooking or before we eat it but 75% of the salt, we consume is already added to the food we eat, especially processed foods such as crisps, biscuits, ready meals soups and pasta sauce.

What is Salt? Common salt is made up of primarily sodium chloride (NaCl). In its natural form as a crystalline mineral, sodium chloride is known as halite. Sodium chloride is an ionic compound which means its components are held together through ionic bonds.

Where Does Salt Come From? The largest source of salt on Earth comes from seas and oceans. This is where the term “sea salt” comes from. Underground salt deposits and salt flats are the results of dried-up seas and oceans. So in reality, all salt could be classified as “sea salt” since all salt came from the sea at some point.

However, the term “rock salt” is commonly used to describe salt that is mined from the ground.

Iodized Salt. Origin. Iodine is an essential element enabling the healthy functioning of the human thyroid gland. Too little iodine can produce an enlargement of the thyroid gland called a goiter. More seriously, iodine deficiency is a leading cause of mental retardation. Severe cases of iodine deficiency can lead to stillbirth and miscarriage, while more mild iodine deficiency can affect brain development and learning.

Characteristics. Iodized salt consists mainly of sodium chloride so its crystal structure is cubic. This cubic structure can be seen in the image above. But some grains of salt appear to have a rounded shape. This is not its natural crystalline form.

Uses. Iodized salt, commonly referred to as table salt, makes up about 70% of salt sales in the United States. In many American households, iodized salt is used in almost all cooking that requires salt. However, many processed foods do not contain iodized salt.

Himalayan Pink Salt. Origin. Himalayan Pink Salt is mined primarily in Pakistan’s Khewra Salt Mines. Since Himalayan Pink Salt is mined from underground salt deposits, it is considered a rock salt.

Characteristics. Himalayan Pink Salt can be found in a variety of colors ranging from white to a deep red color. Himalayan Pink Salt contains over 80 trace minerals which causes it to have a less cubic crystal structure than typical sodium chloride.

Uses. Himalayan Pink Salt is commonly used in cooking, brining, and for bath and beauty products. Due to its interesting coloration and translucent nature,

Himalayan Pink Salt is also commonly used in lamps for household decoration.

Large blocks of Himalayan Pink Salt are also used to cook and serve food.

Celtic Salt. Origin. Celtic Salt, also known as Grey Salt or Sel Grisin French, is sea salt that has been evaporated by the sun and wind and is harvested using wooden rakes from the bottom of salt pans, however grey salt is also produced throughout northern Atlantic regions and in Thailand.

Characteristics. Celtic Salt is often light grey in color, but it will vary depending on how much interaction the salt was allowed to have with the clay. Since it is a sea salt, it contains numerous trace minerals.

Uses. Celtic Salt is commonly used in cooking, brining, and for many bath and beauty products. However, due to its moisture and clumping, it isn't often used as a table salt because it would have difficulty smoothly being poured out of a typical salt shaker.

Hawaiian Red Sea Salt. Origin. Hawaiian Red Sea Salt, also known as Alaea Salt, is made from Hawaiian sea salt which has been mixed with red Hawaiian volcanic clay called alaea. Today however, most alaea sea salts sold in the United States today are not made in Hawaii, but are actually produced in California. Authentic Hawaiian alaea salt can often be very expensive.

Characteristics. Like Himalayan Pink Salt, Hawaiian Red Sea Salt is very rich in trace minerals, but ultimately it gets its reddish color from the iron oxide it contains. It is also commonly used in bath and beauty products. Many of its nutrients can be absorbed through the skin and used to draw out unwanted toxins. This makes alaea salt very popular in exfoliating skin scrubs and is frequently used in spa treatments.

Hawaiian Black Lava Salt. Origin. Hawaiian Black Lava Salt is sea salt that is harvested using solar evaporation. It is then combined with activated volcanic carbon which gives this sea salt its unique black coloring.

Characteristics. Like Hawaiian Red Sea Salt, Hawaiian Black Lava Salt is rich in trace minerals since it is harvested from the same ocean waters.

Uses. The carbon in Hawaiian Black Lava Salt would seem an unlikely flavor enhancer, but many find it has a unique nutty flavor. Since carbon does not dissolve well like sodium chloride does, this black salt isn't often used where salt is intended to dissolve in a dish because the carbon would collect undissolved at the bottom. Instead it is often used as a finishing salt on top of cooked dishes.

Rock salt is a natural supplement that can provide health benefits. It is found in most drug stores, supermarkets and online pharmacies, rock salt is available as a

powder, pill supplement, or even as a liquid extract additive in health beverages. Traditionally used as a spice or flavor addition in cooking, rock salt is also available as an over - thecounter health supplement. Many of these minerals, such as calcium and magnesium, are vitally important to normal organ function within the body.

Conclusion. Common salt contains 97% NaCl and 2.5% additives. 15% of trace minerals of 84 elements give extra energy to the homeostatic system in the body system to give a healthy condition. Rock salt is used as a home remedy for curing many disorders and ailments such as relief from rheumatic pain and herpes, inflammation and irritation from insect bites. Consumption of rock salt along with lemon juice can help in eliminating stomach worms and controlling vomiting. It also provides relief against pain. It helps in maintaining the flow of salivary and digestive juices.

Used internet sources:

1. <http://www.saltinstitute.org/news-articles/iodized-salt/>
2. <http://www.pmdc.gov.pk/?p=KhewraSaltMines>
3. <http://www.atlasobscura.com/places/khewra-salt-mines>
4. http://www.nytimes.com/2006/06/13/science/13find.html?_r=0
5. <http://www.maldonsalt.co.uk/About-Salt-What-is-Salt.html>
6. <http://www.vegkitchen.com/tips/a-guide-to-salt-varieties/>
7. <http://www.thespicehouse.com/spices/hawaiian-black-and-red-sea-salt>